

Financial Statements Evaluation

Edwin Amuga

Analysis of the concepts, features and importance of costs and accounting in making decisions in health and social care

Firm knowledge of a number of cost concepts is required by organizations in decision making. Different characteristics are exhibited by different costs. It is imperative to understand the following cost concepts when in the task of reviewing a business case as they help determine the path to be taken. Effective cost accounting comes with a number of advantages such as the ability to create consistent information that can be applied in reporting direct and indirect costs, their percentage break down and tracing the outcomes of costs with time. The information can also be used to create effective outcome reports to be used in management and making leadership decisions.

Fixed, Mixed and Variable Costs

Affixed cost does not change in lock step with activity level, such as rent. Variable costs like direct materials on the other hand will change with changes in the activity level. Mixed costs are those that change with activity, for example, the lease payments when the facility is shuttered.

By-product costs are not significant since they are considered part of the production costs of the main product and therefore during the selling of the by-products, no cost is considered too low, they are just profits.

Allocated costs are allocated because they are needs of the accounting standards especially for the financial statements production. There exists no cause-effect between the additional overhead incurrence and one additional production unit creation.

Discretionary costs are those that do not cause any short-term harm to the healthcare facility when dropped. They include staff maintenance and training. In the long run, they have a negative effect when the expenditures are delayed. It should therefore be understood by managers that their decisions to cut back costs may have impacts over a period of time.

Step costs are fixed costs incurred when a large investment is made in response to increase in activity level (Bodie, 2013). This is a step to make a shift in production and is therefore referred to as step cost. The volumes of activity at which step costs are incurred should be understood by managers and may be serviced by delaying other costs like sales or work outsourcing. All the above noted concepts are any management decisions' critical element.

International Public Sector Accounting Standards IPSAS

Full implementation of IPSAS raises an organizations financial reporting as it is a critical element of governance and management; improvements which are important parts of healthcare organizations reform process. Increased transparency is a requirement in the full implementation of IPSAS as a reform process allowing for the organizations health and financial performance understanding. This reform supports assets and liability management, governance and facilitates the decision-making processes. IPSAS compliance necessitates the introduction of enhanced system of internal control so that additional financial reporting requirements are supported. The following significant changes in the organization have arisen from the full implementation of the international public sector accounting standards in the financial statements.

Full after-service health insurance actuarial valuation has earned recognition in the accounts including estimated costs for employees and retired staff future health insurance costs. Long-term staff liability gives the reflection of the unfunded balance. There is a plan in place to fund the unfunded part of the liability, but the organization will only achieve the full funding by 2022 based on actuarial projections. Other staff benefits such as the death and disability compensation, accrued annual leave and termination benefits like the repatriation travel and grants are registered under liability in the accounts during the full actuarial valuation. Inventories have in the full actuarial valuation been registered under assets (Bodie, 2013). These include medicines and vaccine, publications and humanitarian supplies and have been registered therein as assets until they are sold, distributed or until they are expired in use. Enhanced stewardship and management of logistics is achieved by better review of the extent and location of inventories.

Under these standards, equipment, property and plant that encompass building, land, equipment, vehicle and fixtures and fittings are treated as assets and amortized over their useful lives. However, IPSAS permits the full valuation of these assets after a period of five years for the estimation of their full values to establish their residual useful lives and accumulated depreciations (Kou, Peng & Wang, 2014). These standards require that accrual accounting is used so that all revenues and expenses are recognized in the financial statements for the periods that they relate to. Revenue is recorded when an agreement is signed as opposed to when the cash is received. Expenses are on the other hand recognized when the goods and services are received and not when the commitments and payments are made.

There is also an important change in policy for estimating the allowance for 'doubtful account receivable'. At the end of the year, full allowance was made for amounts that were not

paid in the past that resulted in the assessed contribution revenue to accounting on cash basis. IPSAS requirement states that this allowance is recognized for the amounts that may be in doubt. This amount constitutes any amount that have been outstanding for more than two years or rescheduled (Kou, Peng & Wang, 2014).

The programme budget preparation has not been impacted on by the implementation of IPSAS which is still presented on the basis of cash. A greater explanation is required during the comparison with figures in the programme budget and actual results as this differs from the accrual accounting basis. The programme budget still operates on a two-yearly basis in which expenses are reported on an annual basis.

A critical analysis of the financial statements to assess their financial position

Preparation Basis

Annual organizational financial statements were made on financial instruments historical cost adjustment at fair value with incorporation of International Financial Reporting Standards Conforming Policies. Application of these standards has been consistent with exceptions on the adoptions and interpretation of new standards that have been effected in the year ended.

Consolidation Basis

The organization affects returns by way of power over entity since it has power over entity in an exposition and has entity involvement variable rights. Nordic hospitals' interests are not recognized together with consolidated entities' net assets non-controlling interest. They instead are rather recognized within equity. Losses attributed to non-controlling interest are

allocated to them regardless of whether the debit balances are being recognized for non controlling interests.

Combination of Business

Acquisition methods application account for these in that in the date of acquisition, contingent liabilities of the acquiree get fair value valuation. Goodwill is the basis for consideration of any identifiable net assets excesses transfer over fair value. Any shortfall is therefore below the fair value is recognized and either loss or profit in the acquisition period. At the date of acquisition, contingent considerations are fairly and later carried at amortized cost. Later changes are recognized according to IAS loss and profit at fair value of contingent considerations. The management as adopted a policy of accounting to ensure that forward obligations acquire the remaining non controlling interest shares as the acquisition of 100% beneficial ownership. This is a consideration under more fair presentation of the combination of businesses.

Equipment

Equipment is initially measured at costs and later with less accumulated losses due to impairment and depreciations. There is always an annual assessment of residual values and useful lives. Any recordable change is therefore accounted for as estimate changes with international accounting standards.

Intangible Standards

These were in the past recognized at cost and are subsequently estimated less losses due to amortization and impairment. Useful lives and residual values in this case get annual assessment with changes accounted for as estimate changes as stipulated in the international accounting standards.

Financial Instruments

Classification and initial recognition of financial instruments in case the trust engages in contractual agreements are done with the basis on cost fair value as received or given considerations. Given considerations can be financial liabilities or equity instruments whereas received considerations can be financial assets. Given considerations are initially classified according to contractual arrangement substance.

Costs of transactions are part of financial instruments initial measurements and not in the fair value through profits and losses and are measured later as mentioned herein. Receivables are under amortized cost with reference to the effective interest rate methods with deductions of impairment allowance.

Cash and Cash Equivalents

These instruments carrying amounts approximates their fair values comprising of call-held deposits, cash at hand and money market instrument investments, bank overdraft net which are all at the organization's disposal for use. They are subsequently stated at amortized costs as subsequent measurements (Posavac, 2015). Listed investments are carried like unlisted investments get carried subsequently fair value on the basis of profit and loss.

Other financial liabilities

These encompass all payables are under amortized costs with the best method for interest rates and the deferred purchase considerations on fair value loss and profit.

Fair value assumption and methods

Fair value is quoted market price at year end for financial instruments that have been traded in an active market. Their fair values that have not been offered for trade in a financial market are determined using various assumptions and methods on the basis of market conditions on the rate of reporting the risk.

A critical evaluation of budgetary processes used by health and social care organizations, such as Anchor Trust.

Budgeting framework

The budget framework, budget methodologies and resource allocation to budgetary activities were considered in overarching budgetary process assessment. The budgetary framework included elements such as the time frame which focus on a 12 month range, tailoring the budget framework to match the operating environment conditions has resulted in an emphasis on long term planning that reflect on multiyear impact of several decisions with more frequent updates, more volatile environment changes, flexible budgetary rules adoption and good budgeting business sense.

In the organization, budgetary framework tailoring to match the real environment required moving to event level budgeting. There was also a trend in the organizations due to

presence of experienced and skilled managers with financial management expertise. Only broad targets were deemed necessary and freedom as given to managers to spend a lot but achieve without reference to spending controls.

Budgeting methodologies

Top-down and bottom-up budget budgeting combination formed the basis of typical methodology for budget creation. The top down setting ensured high level financial outcomes. While the bottom up setting developed the detailed plans and budgets to fit the set constraints.

Incremental budgeting is the most popular due to the fact that it requires a relative lower resource levels. It's also applicable in places where expenditure is more stable and predictable. It can be self-fulfilling prophesy and supports the status quo. Driver based and zero based budgeting method has bettered the value for money decisions and ensured reduction of cost and efficiency. This makes organizations more effective and able to respond to change.

Resource Allocation to Budgeting Activities

In most cases, finance function percentage efficiency is greater than the whole organizations percentage efficiency, suggesting that lower resource levels are being to finance and budgeting even at times when financial experience is supposed to be at premium to organizations. This practice succeeds along term trend of integrating other directorates and finance function. This has always in the recent past taken the shape of 'business partnering' in both private and public sectors.

Finance function resource allocations of the organization despite the fact that financial skills and expertise are recommended to be at premium. To be more successful, the organization should integrate finance functions with other directorates in the organization in the form of business partnering. This case study group reveals that there's a gap in the organization posing a challenge to finance functions in the articulation and demonstration of the value of good budgeting in the sense of increased efficiency and enhanced information for decision making. Intertwined with good budgeting value is the activity analysis increment over data capture activity. The organizations current financial pressures mean that additional analysis can only be derived from transactional activity further efficiencies. Data analysis forms the basis on which finance function talents and good financial outcomes are derived. This means that during financial constraints, it's advisable to review talents.

Ratios to evaluate the financial performance

Anchor trust an organization's bottom line profit margin best indicates its health financially and long term liability. For accurately evaluate anchor trust's financial health, it is imperative to consider a number of financial metrics, that is; liquidity, profitability and efficiency. Profitability is the most widely known measurement for an organization's health. A number of ratios exist that can help gauge an organization's financial health and viability including total debt, net profit and others that affect the balance sheet and income statement financial ratios general trend is an important consideration in the need to evaluate financial health.

Liquidity

This is a key factor in the assessment of an organization's financial health and encompasses the cash amount and easily-convertible-to-cash assets that the organization owns so that it can effectively manage its short-term debt obligations. An organization can only survive in the long term if it can survive the short term.

There are two common liquidity measurement metrics; that is, current ratio and the quick ratio (Keating, 2014). The acid test in the measurement of liquidity is the quick ratio since it's the most precise measure of the two, due to the fact that it excludes from assets the inventories and current long term debt from liabilities in dividing the current assets by current liabilities. By this, it offers a more realistically practical indication of the organization's short term obligation management with assets and cash on hand. A below 1.0 quick ratio is a red flag as it indicates that current liabilities exceed current assets.

$$\text{Liquidity} = \text{current assets}/\text{current liabilities}$$

Operating Efficiency

This is also a key factor to the organization's financial success since the best indicator to the organization's efficiency is its operating margin (Sing, Durroch & Ashford, 2014). It indicates how the organization controls its cost since it shows the operating margin after the deduction of the variable costs of production and marketing. Good management is healthy to the organization as it overcomes temporary problems as opposed to bad management that can lead to

a collapse. From the financial analysis, the company needs to scale down on the operating costs (Wolf, 2015).

Operating efficiency = turnover less operating costs

Profitability

The organizations net profitability is its bottom-line evaluating factor a part form liquidity, basic insolvency and operating efficiency. An organization must in the long run attain and maintain profitability to survive as opposed to the short run in which it can survive on creditors and investor goodwill. Net margin is the best viable option for evaluating an organization's profitability, which is the ratio of profits to total revenues. It is important to consider the net margin since a small profit unit is not sufficient to gauge an organizations financial health. A company can in some instance register profit in millions but still reflect less than 1% net margin, meaning that a slight increase in operating efficiency or competition can land the company in the red flag region. A large net margin is a greater margin of financial safety and suggests that it is in a better position financially to commit to growth and expansion.

Proposed managerial decisions

The management of anchor trust should approach ways of improving the financial health of the organization. This can be achieved by looking for ways to increase income if the organization is to survive or longer. Another way is to scale down in the operating costs through reducing the wage bill by cutting down on the number of staff as it is in the increase, as

compared to the previous years. Another one is to approach avenues that would help reduce the expenditure by cutting down on the spending on non-basic needs of the trust. The last option to tame the deteriorating financial health is downsizing and selling of unused assets.

References

Bodie, Z. (2013). *Investments*. McGraw-Hill.

Estampe, D., Lamouri, S., Paris, J. L., & Brahim-Djelloul, S. (2013). A framework for analysing supply chain performance evaluation models. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 142(2), 247-258.

Keating, S. B. (Ed.). (2014). *Curriculum development and evaluation in nursing*. Springer Publishing Company.

Kou, G., Peng, Y., & Wang, G. (2014). Evaluation of clustering algorithms for financial risk analysis using MCDM methods. *Information Sciences*, 275, 1-12.

Posavac, E. (2015). *Program evaluation: Methods and case studies*. Routledge.

Singh, S., Darroch, J. E., & Ashford, L. S. (2014). Adding it up: The costs and benefits of investing in sexual and reproductive health 2014.

Wolf, P. (2015). *Evaluation of the DC Opportunity Scholarship Program: impacts after one year*. Maroon Ebooks.

Task 2

A Complete review of how costing design and costing systems are applied in your organization

Cost Accounting in Nordic hospitals

Hospital managers, policymakers and clinicians require accurate hospital costs for the improvement of transparency and efficiency. A number of methods have been in use in the direct cost allocation and the Agreement of the factors has not been fully understood. The agreement of top-down and bottom up unit costs have also been approached herein. There has been an increasing reliance on hospital accounting practices due to the prevailing healthcare reforms going on all over the world. Efficiency and transparency is in pursuit in resource constrained environments for the estimation of cost of hospitals services. Diagnosis related group based payment system is the basis in which hospitals in developed nations are funded. This increases the need for inefficiency location and elimination especially in scenarios where the production cost exceeds the cost of services. This has stimulated the need to have patient level cost estimates so that resource utilization can accurately be measures by payers, policy makers and hospitals.

Several factors including heterogeneity, labor intensity and complexity of the process of production have made it difficult to determine costing. Cost variations have been established to result from patient and provider characteristics, efficiency, clinical activity and the method of costing. There are three steps involving in the allocation of costs to patients, namely; hospital overhead costs allocation to departments, hospital overhead costs allocation patients and department direct cost allocation to patients. This paper gives undue focus to the third step since there is lack of standardization, as the methods of costing are employed in the direct cost of department allocation to patients.

Two steps that have been fronted in the classification of costing methodologies based on the accuracy level (Feischman & Parker, 2015).. The first is the aggregate level and the patient

level gross costing also known as microcosting. The components of cost are valued by cost allotment from comprehensive sources the patient level resource consumption top-down. Average unit costs per patient are brought about by top-down microcosting results while patient level unit cost are fronted by bottom up microcosting. Different nations use these differently; Germany, Netherlands, Sweden and Finland have in place the bottom-up method, France, Estonia and England employ the top-down method.

The costing method choice significantly affects the estimates costs if all other things remain equal. There are studies that have looked into the agreement of both methods and found that they moderate at best.

The hospital under study employs the bottom-up method as it considers it more accurate and relevant than the top-down method. This is because of the hospital's large labor and overhead proportion (Feischman & Parker, 2015).. Cost identification at the patient level is considered time consuming and expensive, the bottom up method is therefore the most recommended in a hospital setting since it might not have significant effect, that is, labor effects on the total cost.

In contrast, France employs top-down microcosting by individual operation aggregate cost allocation. On another hand, a given procedure in a different setting will always have the same cost allocation. The fact that this method ignores individual patient's resource consumption variations is its biggest limitation.

Another bottom-up microcosting method in service industry is the Activity-Based costing and has in existence for over three decades. This method assesses specific resource actual amount that contribute to a service (Feischman & Parker, 2015). This method of costing and

accounting method has limitations that lie on the complexity and implementation cost, a fact that explains its low application in hospitals.

The focus of this paper is on Nordic hospital accounting system actual design and cost use. It also focuses on the management control system and accounting data cost in hospitals. This paper came up with a number of observed conclusions.

Nordic university hospitals applies arrange of diversity in the way it designs its cost accounting models. Different configurations have package varieties with varying characteristics. Consequently, arbitrary allocation models and mechanistic characteristics were the basis for designing simple systems. Advanced planning, resource allocation and performance measurement tools are used in some cases. Another conclusion is that there's a link between funding and system design. It is observable that a university hospital a cost accounting model mix. The organization calculates local standard cost per service using an advanced costing system (Feischman & Parker, 2015). The findings that emanate from the calculation power rethinking of traditional contingency studies implying that Management accounting and overall governance in the public sector should be accorded more attention.

There is an immense importance in funding that impacts on the design and management control system use (Drury, 2013). Nordic hospitals survive on very simplified actual cost information versions in which only total costs and volumes are used and compared to the budget. Ad hoc procedures handle arbitrary allocations by taking back surpluses and assess block-grants subjectively. The Nordic hospital is a success story in terms of growth and increased resources due to employment of simplified and arbitrary system. The reason for not using advanced costing systems in rich organizations can only be addressed by further research.

Another observation in the organization is employment of more advanced systems, though they are not used in local activity control. In this scenario, resources are increased in all cases, but it is only in two that these systems are used in local activity control. In this practice, resources are not linked to systems for services or patient costs. Other uses are not strong enough to legitimize the systems (Deegan, 2013). This means that in order to understand it, more research attention should be focused on the hierarchy of multipurpose systems like costing systems. The two cases seem to be strongly informed advanced costing systems applied which are well controlled in the sense that spending is kept within the budget. There is no observed cause and effect relationship financial performance or control and advanced systems use.

The systems are used in the control of activities and are therefore used to inform organizational decision making. The link between organizational decisional making and cost accounting information should be given more research focus.

Advanced Costing System Development in University Hospitals

Empirical studies have shown that a number of factors influence advanced costing system development in university hospitals. An action research by Bodie (2013) on experience Based Longitudinal Study and Ideas of Design Elements in a Management Accounting Model by Keating (2015) came up with three conclusions.

The first conclusion is that the two main forces that influence costing system development in organizations are the new development goals and the need to get rid of costing system errors. These factors have resulted in costing system size and complexity increase. The second conclusion is that the achievements of these ambitions and their impacts on the costing

system have resulted in new system errors (Pasarini, 2014). This in turn has increased costing system design insights helping in the finding of new solutions to correct the emergent errors that developed from adding new details to the system. The third conclusion is that new development initiatives and new system versions have resulted from these forces making the development process incremental. The management of the organization was not willing to scale down ambitions for the costing system use since both of the costing systems and the process had become irreversible. The studies process is summerizable to an incremental and irreversible development process due to ambition changes in the use of costing system, that is, system error reduction and other external factors. The complexity and the size of the costing system increased during the development process.

Improvement recommendations to the costing and pricing systems used Nordic Hospitals

The organizations should adopt the following cost evaluating and improving principles. The following are the recommended principles and undertakings that should be adopted in order to improve costing and pricing systems (Lanen, 2015).

The first is the recognition of the importance costing to good management. This can be achieved by interpretation, measurement and cost presentation in relation to organizational flow of economic goods and services, both in a forward looking context and historically should be employed for a better profit and value drivers understanding.

Another recommendation is the employment of a principle of fitness for purpose. Specific context and purpose of use should inform the preparation of cost information, in with application of three principles, that is, historical and descriptive external reporting, interpretative and diagnostic performance evaluation and analysis and analytical and predictive planning and decision support.

The third recommendation is the adoption of reality driven business models. It is recommendable that cost models are created to show the cause-effect relations and behavioral dynamics of organizational functions. This can be achieved by taking into account the decision makers' needs at all organizational levels through organizational operational and business model, structure, strategy and competitive environment incorporation

Yet another recommendation is cost effectiveness or materiality. Required accuracy levels and measurement cost (i.e cost benefit tradeoff) balance should be reflected on the design, implementation and continuous costing methods, data collection and system improvements (Feischman & Parker, 2015).

Another recommendation for the improvement of costing system is the adoption of overtime comparability and consistency. This can be achieved by systematically collecting and analyzing cost information in a way that ensures comparability over time, either in routine information system or for specific purpose application (Lanen, 2015).

Yet another recommendable principle is transparency and auditability. Cost data definition and sources, non-financial and operational data that underpin them, cost calculation

methods and tools should be designed in a way that make them transparent to users and recorded making review, risk analysis and assurance easy and fast.

Each of the recommended principles applies independently and must not therefore be seen as steps in a process. They can apply in all organizations especially in cases where there are requirement by law that relate to costing, and not cost accounting in achievement of local good practice. It should be noted that law compliance overrides IGPG.

Budgetary targets EVALUATION and master budget for Nordic Hospitals

NORDIC HOSPITAL

THREE MONTH MASTER BUDGET

FISCAL YEAR ENDING 30TH JUNE 2014

Department	JAN	FEB	MARCH
Nursing service			
Medical/surgical	11,050	4650	0
Special care unit	1000	8000	0

Emergency room	3000	3000	0
Nursing home	7600	2600	2800
Operating room, recovery room and anesthesia	39945	20000	0
Central service	920	0	0
Laboratory	40600	0	0
Radiology	395000	30000	20000
pharmacy	700	200	30000
Respiratory	550	0	0
Physical therapy	5900	0	0
Medical records	14300	0	0
Dietary	6785	875	0
Operating and maintain plant	165877	7400	22800

Housekeeping and laundry	45000 780	0 200	0 500
Business office Administration and data processing	3180	1000	1000
Contingency		150000	150000
Totals	742287	227925	227100
Source of funds			
Depreciation expense	279600 110000	279600 140,000	279600 150000
Less: principal payments			
Working capital	169000	139000	129600
EXCESS/PROFIT	400000	230000	230000
Totals	400,000	230000	230000

Steps in preparing master budget

1. An operating profit goal was set, with the intended outcome factored in.
2. The operating expenses were estimated based on the hospitals past expenses.
3. Gross profit was then computed by adding the projected net profit to the expenses.
4. The sales revenues were forecast by determining the percentage of the gross profit out of the sales.
5. The budget as then reviewed based on the sales and other receivables by reducing expenses.
6. The steps above were done to make small budgets of each department then combined into a master budget.

References

- Deegan, C. (2013). *Financial accounting theory*. McGraw-Hill Education Australia.
- DRURY, C. M. (2013). *Management and cost accounting*. Springer.
- Fleischman, R. K., & Parker, L. D. (2017). *What is Past is Prologue: Cost Accounting in the British Industrial Revolution, 1760-1850* (Vol. 6). Routledge.
- Lanen, W. (2016). *Fundamentals of cost accounting*. McGraw-Hill Higher Education.

Passarini, K. C., Pereira, M. A., de Brito Farias, T. M., Calarge, F. A., & Santana, C. C. (2014). Assessment of the viability and sustainability of an integrated waste management system for the city of Campinas (Brazil), by means of ecological cost accounting. *Journal of cleaner production*, 65, 479-488.